

THE ROLE OF MODERN LINGUISTICS AND METHODOLOGY IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation : This article discusses the role and importance of modern linguistics and methods in studying a foreign language. The purpose of the article is to define a new and more convenient way of learning a foreign language.

Key words : Linguistics , education , world science , foreign languages .

Although the issue of effective learning of foreign languages and easier acquisition of new vocabulary has been studied by many scientists, it is always considered a topical issue. Such an approach to this issue . It is natural to be considered in today's world history. Organization of bilingual education, often in the study of a foreign language allows you to deepen and learn several foreign languages. Learning a foreign language is multifaceted is a doctrine and undergoes complex psychological changes in the process. In particular, the process of comparing the mother tongue and the foreign language takes place. from different methods and technologies of teaching in this process is used. Teaching a foreign language by comparing the native language with the help of modern pedagogical technologies gives an effective result. The science of linguistics or linguistics studies and analyzes the tool of communication, which is a unique complex social phenomenon - language as a system - as a whole object. In the same process, it is observed in various forms. This comes from the nature of the language, which has a social character, from the need to study and examine it from different angles, and it is absolutely correct from the point of view of science. Linguistics is manifested in the following forms in the process of learning the language, which is a very powerful symbol of spirituality, the wealth of the nation. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology. The active method of teaching English is represented by the theory of gradual formation serves as a basis for an active concept of teaching. Modern educational development has given rise to a new direction of innovative pedagogy. Innovative - means "introduction (dissemination) of innovation" in English. The socio-psychological aspect of innovation was developed by the American researcher E. Rogers. He studied the classification of innovation process participants, their attitude to innovation, etc. The concepts of novelty and innovation are mutually different in scientific areas. "Innovation" means a tool, new method, methodology, technology. "Innovation" is a process that develops according to certain stages of education. The development of world science is growing and developing day by day. It was this positive development that affected our country as well. Advanced innovative technologies are being applied to our world of science. As a result of this, our President named this year as "Year of Youth Support and Public Health", which increased the responsibility of the youth of our country. It would not be wrong to say that the wide application of advanced, modern innovative technologies in the fields of education has opened the door to many opportunities and goals for young people learning foreign languages. A foreign language is the language of a foreign country. Western European languages (English, Spanish, German, French) and Eastern languages (Arabic, Turkish, Persian, Chinese, Indian) are taught in our republic. These

languages are included in the curricula of educational institutions. The process of teaching all three languages is different. The mother tongue and the second language are learned in a natural situation, and a foreign language is learned in an artificial environment. Communication in a foreign language mainly takes place in the classroom under the guidance of the teacher. Among the three languages, learning and teaching a foreign language differs sharply in certain aspects. This, in turn, requires the use of appropriate foreign language teaching technology. By carefully mastering the achievements of the methodical science, the foreign language teacher will be able to clearly know the standard of language experience of the student and to improve it further. Effective teaching of foreign languages requires knowledge of its methodology. Learning and teaching foreign languages in many ways involves the issues of foreign language teaching methodology from a theoretical point of view depends on the development and creative application of the theory in practice. The subject of the methodology is the process and methods of education through the subject of a foreign language, the science of teaching a foreign language, the study of teacher and student activity is considered the subject of the methodology. The main concepts of methodology - method, method, principle. Didactics is the content of teaching. Methodology means methods and methods of education. Method - the concept of methodology is derived from the Greek-Latin word "methodos-"methodus" and means the means of ways leading to a certain goal. In various literature, the term can be found in narrow and broad meanings. The term "methodology" in a narrow sense refers to the concept related to the concrete lesson process of education. Interpreted as a guided learning process that includes instruction related to lesson planning and preparation of instructional materials. The term "method" in a broad sense refers to the selection, classification and distribution of educational material. The method of translation is mainly in two forms, called grammar-translation and text-translation methods. From the point of view of the grammar-translation method, a foreign language is studied for general educational purposes. Grammatical exercises are performed in order to develop the logical thinking of the language learner. Expressing grammatical knowledge is considered to be the main goal of education. The main principles of this method are as follows:

1. Language learning is based on written speech.
2. Grammar was taken as the subject of study, and the lexicon was chosen accordingly. Grammar exercises were the main method of work.
3. First, grammatical rules were memorized, and then it was recommended to make sentences based on the rules.
4. Grammatical forms and the meaning of words are revealed through literal translation.
5. Language material is mastered by literal translation and dry memorization.
6. Limited to individual memorization of words out of context.

Practice is the best way to master all knowledge. The exercise gives a positive result not only in foreign language education, but also in mastering knowledge in all fields. Effective organization of the lesson, the role of the pedagogue and modern pedagogical technologies in it is incomparable. It is important to organize the process of learning a foreign language with a

communicative approach, to bring the next level to the level of intercultural communication, and to achieve such results, it is important to pay attention to the last step, "exercise technology". In order to effectively organize the foreign language teaching process, it is necessary to acquire knowledge of modern pedagogical information and communication technologies.

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